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SOLUTIONS TO PROBLEMS IN DEVELOPING NATIONAL CULTURAL HERITAGE TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract - The article presents the content of the problems identified as a result of research in the organization and development of national cultural heritage tourism in Uzbekistan . It also provides recommendations for solving the identified problems.

Keywords- Strategy, Expedition, Dissertation, Term Paper, Craft, Recreation, Gastronomy, Festival, Tours, Ceremony.

I. INTRODUCTION

A pressing issue at the state level is the emergence of needs in society, which can also be important requirements of the socio-economic life of society. We should use the experience accumulated so far and the results of our research in the field of tourism to identify problems and study their solutions in organizing and developing a new direction in the field of tourism, a type of national cultural heritage tourism, which is currently being studied and included in the strategic directions of the economy of Uzbekistan.

On April 9, our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev held a video conference on increasing the tourism potential of the regions of Uzbekistan . As it turned out, tourism exports in Uzbekistan in recent years have reached \$ 3.5 billion, and last year the flow of foreign tourists exceeded 10 million people. Currently, a strategy is being developed to increase the share of tourism in the Uzbek economy to 7 percent by 2040, and exports to \$ 10 billion. At the meeting, the head of state set new tasks for the development of the tourism sector. At the same time, the implementation of a large part of the tasks set out in the government resolution adopted in this sector six

months ago is delayed. In particular, new types of tourism, such as industrial, geological, scientific, military and government tourism, have not appeared. This data also makes the development of new types of tourism in our country one of the most urgent issues in the tourism sector.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

From our observations on the use of the national heritage of our people in tourism in Uzbekistan, it became clear that so far the results of scientific research in this area have been published in limited numbers [7.8.9.10.11.12.]. This situation indicates that scientific research has not been initiated in the direction of organizing and developing new national cultural heritage tourism in Uzbekistan, and that such an urgent topic as the use of the national heritage of our people in tourism remains outside the attention of both scientists, specialists and entrepreneurs.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

We used methods of logical analysis and synthesis, logical approach of the theory of knowledge, induction and deduction, comparative and factor analysis, time and space, comparison, and monographic observation in the research.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Based on the results of our research, we were able to identify problems in the organization and development of national cultural heritage tourism in our country. According to our conclusions, these problems mainly include the following problems related to the information and popularization of our national culture, national art, national traditions, production of products from national heritage resources, and national games in domestic and international tourism:

1. The issues of organizing and developing a new type of national cultural heritage tourism in Uzbek tourism have not been promoted at scientific conferences and information systems dedicated to the development of the tourism sector.

Therefore, as a result of not including it as a separate topic in the specialized disciplines of the bachelor's and master's education system in the field of tourism, the relevance of using the national heritage of our people in tourism has been overlooked. Therefore, students and masters on this topic would have carried out the initial popularization of the emergence of national cultural heritage tourism development (independent works on national heritage, course works, master's theses, etc.) [4.5.6.].

2. The problem of the lack of organizational mechanisms for the organization and development of new, national cultural heritage tourism, which has the potential to make a potential contribution to the preservation and development of the high spiritual values and spiritual heritage of our people formed over the centuries, and their development in harmony with world culture, the widespread promotion of national culture, and the further strengthening of its place and status in the international cultural space.

3. Problems of inclusion of national culture, national art and national games events held in our country, as well as cultural events and programs organized by cultural centers for foreign tourists in international tourism development programs.

4. Problems of the lack of development of programs to widely cover national cultural events held in our country in foreign media through representatives of diplomatic missions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in foreign countries, to further intensify cultural cooperation with foreign countries in the field of our national culture, and to attract foreign tourists to national cultural events.

5. The problem of substantiating the importance of developing national cultural heritage tourism in conveying the rich values, crafts, customs, traditions, and creative arts of our people to the peoples of the world, the problems of attracting international tourists from all over the world to our districts and villages and organizing their visits to national handicraft houses .

6. Problems in justifying the development of rural tourism, pilgrimage tourism, eco-recreational tourism and gastronomic tourism of national cultural heritage tourism.

7. In international tourism, the problems of showing the unique riches of our national cultural heritage and not defining the tasks of developing international tourism based on these factors.

8. Problems in establishing craft development centers in cities and districts with widely developed folk crafts and creative traditions, restoring and further developing unique types of crafts, and creating market infrastructures for supplying craft products to consumers.

9. Problems in implementing the tasks, instructions and plans set out in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev “On measures to further improve the system of public administration in the fields of tourism, sports and cultural heritage”[1], the Resolution “On the organization of the activities of the Ministry of Tourism and Sports”[2] and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the Regulation on the procedure for the use of tangible cultural heritage objects”[3].

In our opinion, we can find solutions to the problems identified in the organization and development of national cultural heritage tourism in Uzbekistan in each problem itself as follows:

1. The issues of organizing and developing a new type of national cultural heritage tourism in Uzbek tourism should be included in the curriculum of undergraduate and graduate education systems of universities and institutes where tourism education is taught, as part of the block of specialized subjects. As a result, textbooks and manuals on the use of national heritage resources in tourism will be created.

When preparing coursework for bachelors and master's students, they will certainly choose the areas of national heritage that interest them. Also, the fact that scientific conferences dedicated to the development of the tourism industry have designated areas for the development of national cultural heritage tourism in Uzbekistan will also lead to the rapid popularization of national cultural heritage tourism.

2. Including issues of developing organizational, socio-economic mechanisms for organizing and developing new, national cultural heritage tourism in the scientific research plans of departments of universities and institutes that train specialists in the tourism sector in Uzbekistan will yield the expected results in the development of this type of tourism.

3. The Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change of the Republic of Uzbekistan should include in its international tourism development programs programs for national cultural heritage tourism, including national culture, national art and national games events, festivals, and cultural centers of different nationalities, as well as cultural events organized for foreign tourists.

4. The Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change of the Republic of Uzbekistan should develop programs for wide coverage of national cultural events held in our country in foreign media through representatives of diplomatic missions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in foreign countries, further intensification of cultural cooperation with foreign countries in the field of our national culture, and attraction of foreign tourists to national cultural events.

5. District khokimiyats of the regions, district mahalla administrations and activists should understand and be interested in the importance of developing national cultural heritage tourism in conveying the craftsmanship, customs, traditions, and creative arts of our people to the peoples of the world. There is a great opportunity for our districts and villages to attract international tourists from all over the world and organize their economic interest in taking them to national handicraft houses.

6. The Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change of the Republic of Uzbekistan should pay serious attention to strengthening the development of national cultural heritage tourism, rural tourism, pilgrimage tourism, ecological and recreational tourism, and gastronomic tourism.

7. All organizations in the tourism sector of our country must implement the tasks, instructions and plans set out in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev “On measures to further improve the system of state

administration in the fields of tourism, sports and cultural heritage”, the Resolution “On the organization of the activities of the Ministry of Tourism and Sports” and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the Regulation on the procedure for the use of tangible cultural heritage objects”.

8. The success of the sectors, branches and directions of the production of material and non-material products in the national economy certainly depends on strong mutual cooperation. From this point of view, the problems identified above in the organization and development of national cultural heritage tourism can be solved in a short period of time as a result of the cooperation of official organizations in the tourism of our country, scientists in tourism education, specialists and entrepreneurs.

V. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Inclusion of issues of organizing and developing a new type of national cultural heritage tourism in Uzbek tourism as a block of specialized subjects in the curricula of undergraduate and graduate education systems of universities and institutes where tourism education is taught.

2. The Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change of the Republic of Uzbekistan should include in its international tourism development programs national cultural heritage tourism programs, including national culture, national art and national games events, festivals, and cultural centers of various nationalities, as well as cultural events organized for foreign tourists.

3. Incorporate issues of developing organizational, socio-economic mechanisms for organizing and developing new, national cultural heritage tourism into the scientific research agenda of departments of universities and institutes that train specialists in the tourism sector in Uzbekistan.

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